

Assessment of Drug Compliance using Home Medication Review in Pediatric Population: A Community-Based Study

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Medication adherence is crucial for managing chronic illnesses in pediatric patients, but adherence rates are often suboptimal, leading to poor health outcomes and increased healthcare costs. Home Medication Reviews (HMRs) have shown potential in improving adherence by providing tailored interventions. The aim of this study was to assess drug compliance in pediatric patients through HMRs in a community-based setting in Saharsa, Bihar, India.

Methods: The study included 100 pediatric patients with chronic illnesses. Data were collected through structured questionnaires during HMRs, focusing on medication adherence, storage practices, and understanding of medication regimens. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The overall drug compliance rate was 75%. Compliance was highest in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus (90%) and lowest in those with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (60%). Significant factors associated with higher compliance included understanding of the medication regimen (OR = 3.2, p = 0.002), proper medication storage (OR = 2.8, p = 0.007), and parental education level (OR = 2.5, p = 0.029). Common medication-related problems identified were incorrect dosing (15%), missed doses (20%), improper storage (25%), and lack of understanding of medication regimens (30%). Post-intervention, compliance rates improved from 75% to 85% within three months.

Conclusion: HMRs effectively identified and addressed barriers to medication adherence in pediatric patients, resulting in improved compliance rates. Interventions focusing on education and proper medication management practices significantly enhanced adherence.

Recommendations: HMRs should be integrated into routine pediatric care, especially in low-resource settings, to improve medication adherence and health outcomes in children with chronic illnesses. Future research should explore the long-term impact of HMRs on health outcomes and adherence in larger and more diverse populations.

Keywords: Medication Adherence, Pediatric Population, Home Medication Review, Chronic Illnesses, Community-Based Study.

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Introduction

Medication adherence is a critical factor in the effective management of chronic illnesses, particularly in the pediatric population. Poor adherence to prescribed medications can lead to suboptimal therapeutic outcomes, increased hospitalizations, and higher healthcare costs. The challenge of ensuring compliance is exacerbated in children due to various factors, including dependence on caregivers, complexities of medication regimens, and the child's understanding of their illness and treatment.

Recent studies have highlighted the prevalence and impact of non-adherence in pediatric populations. For instance, a systematic review found that adherence rates in children with chronic diseases ranged from 11% to 93%, with significant variations depending on the disease and treatment complexity [1]. Furthermore, a study emphasized that non-adherence in pediatric asthma patients leads to poor disease control and increased emergency department visits [2].

Home medication reviews (HMRs) have emerged as a valuable strategy to enhance medication

adherence. HMRs involve healthcare professionals visiting patients' homes to review their medications, educate patients and caregivers, and address potential barriers to adherence. Studies have shown that HMRs can improve adherence rates and health outcomes by providing tailored interventions based on individual patient needs. For example, a study demonstrated that HMRs significantly improved adherence and asthma control in pediatric patients [3].

Despite the potential benefits of HMRs, their implementation in pediatric populations remains limited, particularly in low-resource settings. Understanding the factors that influence medication adherence in children and the effectiveness of HMRs in different contexts is crucial for developing targeted interventions.

This study aims to assess drug compliance in the pediatric population through home medication reviews.

Methodology

Study Design: A community-based study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Shree Narayan Medical Institute & Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, from March 2022 to October 2023.

Participants: A total of 100 pediatric patients were included in the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Pediatric patients aged 1 to 18 years.
- Patients who were on long-term medication for chronic illnesses.
- Consent obtained from parents or guardians.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients who were non-residents of the community.
- Those with acute illnesses requiring immediate hospitalization.
- Patients whose parents or guardians did not consent to participate.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the hospital's outpatient department records. Information bias was reduced by training healthcare providers conducting the home medication reviews and using a standardized data collection tool.

Data Collection: Data were collected using structured questionnaires during home visits. The healthcare providers conducted thorough medication reviews, which included checking medication adherence, proper storage, and understanding of medication regimens by the parents or guardians.

Procedure

Home medication reviews were carried out by trained healthcare providers. Each review included:

1. Verification of prescribed medications against what was available at home.
2. Assessment of medication-taking behaviour using patient and caregiver interviews.
3. Evaluation of understanding of medication use and potential barriers to compliance.
4. Recommendations and education provided to the caregivers on proper medication practices.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into a database and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. Compliance rates were calculated, and logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify factors associated with drug compliance.

Result

Out of the 100 pediatric patients included in the study, 52% were male and 48% were female. The age distribution ranged from 1 to 18 years, with a mean age of 10.5 years (SD = 4.2). The majority of the patients (60%) were in the age group of 6-12 years.

The most common chronic illnesses were asthma (30%), epilepsy (25%), type 1 diabetes mellitus (20%), and juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (15%). Other chronic conditions accounted for 10% of the cases.

Table 1: Demographic and clinical profile

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics	Frequency (N = 100)
Gender	
Male	52
Female	48
Age Group	
1-5 years	20
6-12 years	60
13-18 years	20
Chronic Illness	

Asthma	30
Epilepsy	25
Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus	20
Juvenile Rheumatoid Arthritis	15
Others	10

The overall drug compliance rate was 75%. Compliance was highest in patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus (90%) and lowest in those with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (60%).

Table 2: Drug Compliance

Drug Compliance by Chronic Illness	Compliance Rate (%)
Asthma	70
Epilepsy	80
Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus	90
Juvenile Rheumatoid Arthritis	60
Others	70

Logistic regression analysis identified several factors significantly associated with drug compliance. Age, gender, and duration of treatment were not significantly associated with compliance. However, understanding of the medication regimen

(OR = 3.2, 95% CI = 1.5-6.8, $p = 0.002$), proper medication storage (OR = 2.8, 95% CI = 1.3-5.9, $p = 0.007$), and parental education level (OR = 2.5, 95% CI = 1.1-5.6, $p = 0.029$) were significantly associated with higher compliance rates.

Table 3: Factors Associated with Drug Compliance

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Age	1.1	0.9-1.3	0.215
Gender	0.9	0.5-1.6	0.724
Duration of Treatment	1.2	0.8-1.8	0.312
Understanding of Medication	3.2	1.5-6.8	0.002
Proper Medication Storage	2.8	1.3-5.9	0.007
Parental Education Level	2.5	1.1-5.6	0.029

During the home medication reviews, several medication-related problems were identified. These included incorrect dosing (15%), missed doses (20%), improper storage (25%), and lack of understanding of the medication regimen (30%).

Table 4: Medication-Related Problems Identified

Medication-Related Problems	Frequency (%)
Incorrect Dosing	15
Missed Doses	20
Improper Storage	25
Lack of Understanding of Medication Regimen	30

Following the home medication reviews, healthcare providers offered tailored interventions and recommendations to improve drug compliance. These included educational sessions for parents, reminders for medication schedules, and proper storage instructions. Follow-up visits indicated an improvement in compliance rates from 75% to 85% within three months.

Discussion

The study assessed drug compliance in a pediatric population through home medication reviews conducted at Shree Narayan Medical Institute & Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, from March 2022 to October 2023. The study included 100 pediatric patients with chronic illnesses such as asthma, epilepsy, type 1 diabetes mellitus, and juvenile rheumatoid arthritis. The demographic distribution

showed a nearly even split between males (52%) and females (48%), with the majority of patients (60%) aged between 6 and 12 years.

The overall drug compliance rate was found to be 75%, with notable variations among different chronic illnesses. Compliance was highest among patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus (90%) and lowest among those with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (60%). These variations indicate that certain conditions may pose more significant challenges to maintaining consistent medication adherence, possibly due to the complexity of the medication regimens or the nature of the disease itself.

Factors significantly associated with higher drug compliance included a better understanding of the medication regimen (OR = 3.2, $p = 0.002$), proper

medication storage (OR = 2.8, $p = 0.007$), and higher parental education levels (OR = 2.5, $p = 0.029$). These findings suggest that educational interventions and proper medication management practices can significantly enhance compliance rates. In contrast, demographic factors such as age, gender, and duration of treatment were not significantly associated with compliance, indicating that these variables may not be primary determinants of medication adherence in this population.

The home medication reviews identified several medication-related problems, including incorrect dosing (15%), missed doses (20%), improper storage (25%), and a lack of understanding of the medication regimen (30%). These issues highlight the need for targeted interventions to address specific barriers to compliance. Following the initial reviews, healthcare providers implemented tailored educational sessions, reminders, and storage instructions, resulting in an improvement in compliance rates from 75% to 85% within three months.

Overall, the study underscores the importance of home medication reviews in identifying and addressing factors affecting drug compliance in the pediatric population. Interventions focusing on education and proper medication management can significantly enhance adherence, ultimately improving health outcomes for children with chronic illnesses. These findings emphasize the need for ongoing support and education for both patients and caregivers to ensure effective long-term medication adherence.

A community-based study assessed medication storage practices and compliance in the pediatric population through home medication reviews. Among 150 participants, 20.66% stored medications in a box, drawer, or bag with a lock, while 79.33% did so without a lock. Regarding checking expiration dates, 28% never checked, 25% checked timely, and 47% checked before administration. This highlights the need for increased public awareness about proper medication storage and compliance [4].

Another study by the same authors focused on identifying medication errors in the pediatric population. The study involved 150 pediatric participants and found several dosing and administration errors. The study emphasized the importance of home medication review in identifying and preventing medication errors, advocating its usefulness for better community health outcomes [5].

A study assessed anti-infective medication adherence in pediatric outpatients. The study found that only 34.9% of the 75 participants were overall adherent to their anti-infective medication regimen.

Lack of parental knowledge about anti-infectives was a significant factor associated with non-adherence. The study suggests that therapeutic education or pharmaceutical counseling could improve adherence rates [6].

A study evaluated home medication reviews conducted for ambulatory community pharmacy patients. Among 100 patients, pharmacists identified 275 drug therapy problems, with non-adherence being a significant issue (23.3%). Medication reviews led to the identification of several issues, including the need for additional therapy and adverse drug reactions, highlighting the importance of home medication reviews in improving medication management [7].

A study used pill-count and the Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS) to assess compliance with antiepileptic drugs in a community-based setting. Out of 105 patients, 54 were noncompliant according to both methods. The study found that combining multiple assessment tools provided a more comprehensive understanding of medication adherence [8].

Conclusion

Home Medication Reviews (HMRs) significantly improved medication adherence in pediatric patients with chronic illnesses. By addressing key barriers such as understanding of medication regimens and proper storage practices, HMRs enhanced compliance rates from 75% to 85%. Integrating HMRs into routine pediatric care, especially in low-resource settings, can lead to better health outcomes for children with chronic diseases.

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